

ABO Blood Group Genotypes, Demographic Characteristics, and Hepatitis B and C in Birnin Kebbi, North-West Nigeria: An Analysis of Association and Prevalence

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Abstract

Background: The expanding hepatitis burden in Nigeria has become a major public health concern, emphasizing the need for new and complementary control approaches. This study looked at the demographic parameters, ABO blood group genotypes, and hepatitis prevalence in Birnin Kebbi, North-West Nigeria.

Methods: The study used a cross-sectional design to collect data from 200 participants who received hepatitis screening at the Federal University Teaching Hospital in Birnin Kebbi between May and November 2023, using standardized questionnaires.

Results: Out of the 200 people screened, 21 (10.5%) tested positive for hepatitis B virus (HBV), however no cases of hepatitis C virus (HCV) were detected. The 41-50 age group had the highest prevalence of HBV (20%), followed by <20 years (18.75%), 31-40 years (12%), and 21-30 years (8.26%). Notably, all HBV-positive cases were males. In terms of ABO blood group genotypes, 12 (57.1%) of the 21 HBV-positive individuals were O+ carriers, 6 (28.6%) were B+, and 3 (14.3%) were A+. However, statistical analysis found no significant relationship ($P > 0.05$) between HBV prevalence and demographic variables or ABO blood group genotypes.

Conclusion: These findings highlight the need for enhanced public awareness of HBV hazards in Birnin Kebbi, particularly among men and those with ABO blood categories A+, B+, and O+. Public health interventions and educational campaigns are critical in addressing the transmission and burden of HBV in these locations.

Keywords: ABO blood groups, Hepatitis B virus, Prevalence, Questionnaire, Nigeria

Introduction

Hepatitis, as a liver inflammation, produced by a number of infectious viruses and noninfectious substances that can result in a variety of health issues, some of which are fatal (1). The hepatitis virus is classified into five strains: type A, B, C, D, and E (2). While they all cause liver disease, their means of

transmission, severity of illness, geographical distribution, and preventative approaches vary (1). Acute hepatitis symptoms include fatigue, fever, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, abdominal discomfort, dark urine, joint pain, and jaundice (3).

Chronic viral hepatitis takes decades to develop and can cause liver cirrhosis, hepatocellular carcinoma,

hepatic fibrosis, and steatosis, resulting in substantial morbidity and mortality globally (4,5). The disease's major medical consequences are acute flares and extrahepatic manifestations (6).

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) are both blood-borne infections and the most deadly forms of viruses (7). HBV belongs to the *Hepadnaviridae* family and has a reverse-transcribed, partially double-stranded genome (3). It infects by puncturing the skin or coming into touch with infected blood or bodily fluids (3). HCV, on the other hand, belongs to the *Flaviviridae* family of positive-strand RNA viruses and is transmitted by contact with virus-carrying blood or body fluids containing blood (3). HBV is more infectious, while HCV is the leading cause of chronic hepatitis (8). Both strains impose a massive health and economic burden on the world; an estimated 354 million people live with HBV or HCV, and for the most majority, testing and treatment are out of reach (1). HBV-related cirrhosis caused an estimated 331,000 fatalities in 2019, whereas HBV-related liver cancer caused an estimated 192,000 deaths, up from 156,000 in 2010 (6). Approximately 1.5 million new HCV infections occur each year, resulting in 290,000 fatalities (9). HBV and HCV, together, are responsible for approximately 90% of hepatitis fatalities (3). The medical cost of treating HCV ranges from \$952 to \$8224, depending on the stage of the disease (10). It was estimated that the worldwide economic burden of HBV between 2022 and 2050 will exceed \$780 billion if preventive measures were not implemented (11).

The majority of HBV and HCV infections occur in underdeveloped nations, with over 91 million Africans affected (12,13). It is a silent epidemic across the continent (14). In 2020, Africa represented for 26% of the global HBV and HCV burden, with 125,000 deaths (13). In Nigeria, the prevalence of HBV is 8.1%, while HCV is 1.1% among adults aged 15 to 64 (14). More than 20 million people in the country have hepatitis B, C, or both; nevertheless, more than 80% of those infected are unaware of their condition (14). The annual cost of maintaining a chronic HBV patient in Nigeria is ₦564,959 (\$1,487) (15). There is a lack of information on the cost of managing HCV in the country.

The high prevalence and accompanying mortality, as well as the economic burden of HBV and HCV, have forced some families into poverty and reduced productive hours, necessitating immediate action. Fortunately, a World Health Organization study concluded that immunization, diagnostic tests, medicines, and information campaigns could avert 4.5 million premature deaths in low- and middle-income countries by 2030 (1). Furthermore, studies by Jefferies and colleagues (16), Oladele and colleagues

(17), and Yahaya and colleagues (18,19) found that ABO blood group genotypes and demographic characteristics, among other factors, influence susceptibility to hepatitis and response to treatment, which, when considered, may lead to better outcomes. Studies in Birnin Kebbi, north-west Nigeria, including those by Yakubu and colleagues (20) and Bashar and colleagues (4), have revealed a high frequency and burden of hepatitis, but there is a lack of literature on the effect of ABO blood group genotypes and demographic variables. This information can be used to supplement existing strategies to reduce the disease's growing burden. The current study aims to establish the prevalence, ABO blood group genotypes, and demographic characteristics of hepatitis patients in Birnin, Kebbi, Nigeria.

Materials and methods

Description of the study area

This investigation was carried out at the Federal University Teaching Hospital in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria (Figure 1). Birnin Kebbi is Kebbi State's capital and the Gwandu Emirate's administrative seat. It is located in the North-West geopolitical zone of the country at latitude 12°26'1.820" N and longitude 4°21'77.34" E (Figure 1).

Sudan and Guinea Savannah combine to form the state's natural vegetation. However, continuous anthropogenic activity has affected the natural vegetation. The climate is mostly dry from October to May, with wet weather the rest of the year. The average annual rainfall is 740 mm, with the rainy season lasting from April to October, peaking in June, July, August, and September. During hot and cold periods, temperatures can reach 40°C and drop to 15°C. The hospital is the state's primary hospital, so it is an appropriate setting for the current study.

Study design and data collection

This is a cross-sectional study that took place between May 6, 2023 and November 5, 2023, and focused on persons who used the laboratory services of the Federal University Teaching Hospital in Birnin Kebbi to assess their hepatitis status. The sampling period was chosen to encompass the two primary seasons (dry and wet) experienced in the study sites. Comprehensive medical data about the participants was obtained directly from the hospital's laboratory section utilizing a structured, standardized checklist of patients' registers. To assure the validity and

trustworthiness of the information, a health information management specialist thoroughly examined and vetted the register. The register is divided into two sections: I and II.

Section I covered socio-demographic information, including age, gender, and religion. Meanwhile, Section II provided medical and health-related information, notably the ABO blood group genotypes, rhesus factor, and each individual's hepatitis status (positive or negative).

Sample size determination

Using equation 1, the sample size was determined (21):

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Here, N represents the number of people that went to the health facility for hepatitis screening between May 6th and November 5th, 2023, and e specifies the level of precision, which normally ranges from 0.10 to 0.01 (i.e., 10% to 1%).

In our scenario, with an accuracy level (e) of 5% and an initial population size (N) of 276, we calculate n as follows:

$$n = 276 / (1 + 276 (0.05)^2) \approx 199.82$$

Rounding up, the sample size was 200.

Eligibility criteria

The criteria for inclusion were eligible medical records of all individuals who received hepatitis screening at the health facility between May 6th and November 5th, 2023. Individuals who gave their consent for the study and had complete medical records were considered eligible.

Exclusion criteria include persons beyond the declared duration and those with incomplete records.

Ethical approval and consent to participate

The Ethics Committee of Nigeria's Federal University Birnin Kebbi approved this study (FUBK/2024/021). The research strictly followed the Committee's criteria for conducting studies with human volunteers. Before accessing the patients' medical records, they or their legal guardians provided written informed consent. The confidentiality and anonymity of all gathered information were strictly preserved throughout the investigation.

All procedures were carried out in compliance with the ethical principles described in the Declaration of Helsinki for Medical Research with Human Subjects, which was first approved in 1964 and most recently modified in October 2024.

Validation of tool

This study involved both internal and content validation. Each question was statistically validated to investigate construct validity. Patients' illness status was determined through manual validation of physical records and a well-designed questionnaire. These strategies offer a trustworthy measure of validity.

Data analysis

The data was displayed in a tabular fashion with frequency distributions and percentages using Microsoft Excel 2019. Charts were created using Excel 2016. The Chi-square test was used to examine the relationship between HBV prevalence, blood group genotypes, and demographic characteristics using SPSS version 20. P-values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic data of the participants

Table 1 shows the age, gender, and religion of the participants who agreed to participate in the study. The age group 21 to 30 years had the highest amount of participants, with 121 (60.5%), followed by 31 to 40 years, with 50 (25%). Participants under the age of 20 accounted for 16 (8%), those aged 41 to 50 accounted for 10 (5%), and those aged 51 to 60 had the fewest number of participants, with 3 (1.5%). Males numbered 198 (99%) of the participants, while females made up only 2 (1%). Table 1 shows that 189 (94.50%) of the participants were Muslims, with 11 (5.5%) identifying as Christians.

Figure 2 displays the participants' respective local government areas of origin. Birnin Kebbi had the most participation, accounting for 65% of the total, followed by Maiyama (7%), Gwandu (5%), and Bunza (4%). Other local governments, including Yauri, Jega, Argungu, and Augie, contributed 3% of the total. Zuru contributed up 2%, while Kardi made up 1.5%. Mungadi, Kamba, and Kalgo recorded 1% each.

Figure 1. Map showing the study area

Table 1. Demographic data of the participants

Variables	Age	Frequency	Percentage %
Age	<20	16	8
	21-30	121	60.5
	31-40	50	25
	41-50	10	5
	51-60	3	1.5
Total		200	100%
Gender	Male	198	99
	Female	2	1
Total		200	100%
Religion	Muslim	189	94.5
	Christianity	11	5.5
Total		200	100%

Figure 2. Local government areas of the participants

Table 2. ABO blood group genotypes of the participants

Blood group	Frequency	Percentage (%)
A ⁺	20	10
A ⁻	4	2
B ⁺	38	19
B ⁻	10	5
AB ⁺	2	1
AB ⁻	0	0
O ⁺	120	60
O ⁻	6	3
Total	200	100%

Table 3. Age distribution among the HBV-positive participants

Variables	Age group	Number Examined	Frequency of HBV positives	Percentage (%) prevalence	χ^2 -Value	P-Value (P<0.05)
Age	<20	16	3	18.75	3.234	0.519
	21-30	121	10	8.26		
	31-40	50	6	12.00		
	41-50	10	2	20.00		
	51-60	3	0	0		
Total		200	21	10.50		

Table 4. Gender distribution among the HBV-positive participants

Variables	Gender	Number Examined	Frequency of HBV positives	Percentage (%) prevalence	χ^2 -Value	P-Value (P<0.05)
Gender	Male	198	21	100	0.237	0.800
	Female	2	0	0		
Total				100%		

Table 5. ABO blood group genotypes distribution among the HBV-positive participants

S/N	Blood group	Number Examined	Frequency of HBV positives	Percentage (%) prevalence	χ^2 -Value	P-Value (P<0.05)
1.	A ⁺	20	3	14.3	6.296	0.391
2.	A ⁻	4	0	0		
3.	B ⁺	38	6	28.6		
4.	B ⁻	10	0	0		
5.	AB ⁺	2	0	0		
6.	AB ⁻	0	0	0		
7.	O ⁺	120	12	57.1		
8.	O ⁻	6	0	0		
Total		200	21	100%		

ABO blood group genotypes of the participants

Table 2 shows the ABO blood group genotypes of the individuals. persons with blood group O⁺ had the highest number, with 120 (60%), followed by B⁺ with 38 (19%), A⁺ with 20 (10%), B⁻ with 10 (5%), O⁻ with 6 (3%), A⁻ with 4 (2%), AB⁺ with 2 (1%) persons, and AB⁻ with 0.

Prevalence of Hepatitis B and C virus among the participants

Of the 200 individuals, 21 (10.5%) tested positive for HBV and none for HCV.

Prevalence of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) based on age groups

The prevalence of HBV by age group is given in Table 3. Among the 21 HBV positive participants, age class 41-50 had the highest prevalence with 2 (20.00%), followed by age class <20 with 3 (18.75%), age class 31-40 with 6 (12.00%), and age class 51-60 with 0 (0%). However, the findings revealed no significant connection (P>0.05) between HBV positives and participant age categories.

Prevalence of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) based on genders

Table 4 shows the gender of participants who tested positive for HBV. All 21 HBV positive subjects were male. Furthermore, the data revealed no significant connection (P>0.05) between HBV positives and participant gender.

Prevalence of hepatitis B virus (HBV) based on ABO blood group genotypes

The distribution of ABO blood group genotypes among HBV-positive participants is shown in Table 5. O⁺ had the most participants (12/57.1%), followed by B⁺ (6/28.6%) and A⁺ (3/14.3%). All other blood group genotypes yielded 0 results. There was no significant correlation (P<0.05) between HBV positivity and blood types among subjects.

Discussion

Kebbi State's indigenous population is mostly made up of Hausa, Fulani, and Zuru ethnic groupings, with Islam as the predominant religion (18). Malaria, typhoid, and hepatitis B are common diseases in the state, most likely due to a high mosquito population, a lack of drinkable water, and a lack of awareness (18). The current study was to evaluate the demographic

parameters, ABO blood group genotypes, and hepatitis prevalence in Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria. To do this, relevant information was acquired from individuals who used the city's Federal University Teaching Hospital laboratory services for hepatitis screening. Demographic data revealed that the majority of participants who tested positive for the hepatitis virus were adult males aged 21 to 30, with the majority identifying as Muslims. However, no significant relationship was discovered between these demographic variables and the prevalence of hepatitis. These findings are consistent with those of Adepoju and colleagues (22), who found that HBV and HCV cases in Birnin Kebbi were primarily among people under the age of 40, particularly men. Yakubu and colleagues (20) discovered higher rates of HBV among participants aged 26-30 years in Birnin Kebbi, while Bashar and colleagues (4) identified a greater prevalence among males aged 20-39. The higher illness prevalence in the current study's age categories of 21-30 and 31-40 years may be linked to increased sexual activity and social connections, particularly among self-employed individuals (20). Males are more likely to share sharp tools, notably in barbershops and with nail cutters, which may explain the disease's increased frequency (23). This behavior is especially prevalent among males in Birnin Kebbi. Thus, the disease's high incidence among males implies horizontal transmission via shared sharp items. The overrepresentation of Muslims among patients reflects the religious makeup of the study area. The findings of this study revealed that 10.5% (21) of the total individuals tested positive for HBV, however none tested positive for HCV. These findings are consistent with those of Yakubu and colleagues (20), Adepoju and colleagues (22) and Bashar and colleagues (4), who also found a significant incidence of the virus in Birnin Kebbi. In contrast, whereas the current study did not detect HCV, Adepoju and colleagues (22) discovered the disease among study participants. Similarly, Haruna and colleagues (24) identified HCV in a study conducted in Jega, Kebbi State. The current study's failure to find HCV may be due to a lack of access to a bigger sample size. It may also indicate a drop in disease prevalence, given the 10.5% HBV prevalence identified in the current study is lower than the 19.6% prevalence reported by Bashir and colleagues (4). The current study's 10.5% prevalence is greater than the Nigerian prevalence of 7% reported in a comprehensive review and meta-analysis by Fofana and colleagues. (25). According to Ajuwon and colleagues (12), north-west Nigeria has the highest prevalence of HBV, which could be attributable to low infant immunization rates compared to other parts of the country. HBV is generally more common than other subtypes,

according to the current study, because the virus is most commonly transmitted from mother to child during birth and delivery, in early childhood, and through contact with blood or other body fluids during sex with an infected partner, unsafe injections, or exposure to sharp instruments (26).

The findings also revealed that 12 (57.1%) of the 21 HBV positives were ABO blood group O+, followed by B+ with 6 (28.6%) and A+ with 3 (14.3%) persons. All other blood group genotypes showed 0 results. This finding is consistent with Yahaya and colleagues (27) who found that ABO blood group O+ was the most common blood group among HBV-infected students at Federal University Birnin Kebbi in Nigeria. Oladeinde and colleagues (28) similarly found a high incidence of O+ and a low prevalence of AB among HBV patients in Edo State, south-south Nigeria. Similarly, Oladele and colleagues (17) found that HBV patients in Lagos, Nigeria were more likely to have ABO blood group O and rhesus positive, followed by type A, B, and AB. However, in a research conducted in Turkey by Genc (29), type A was more common. Similarly, Mohammadali and Pourfathollah (30) investigated the incidence of type A and low type O blood groups among Iranian blood donors. The high incidence of O+ among patients (and, by extension, among other disorders) could be attributed to the blood group's evolutionary success, which causes those who carry it to undergo less severe forms of sickness (27). Gilmiyarova and colleagues (31) found that carriers of blood group O are more resistant to disease than non-O carriers, with the exception of *H. pylori*-associated gastrointestinal disorders. Furthermore, Thakur and colleagues (32) noted that O blood has intrinsic immunity, which has a preventive effect against disease. This could explain why evolutionary success favored the blood type, resulting in a large population of carriers. Some studies have shown high rates of non-O blood groups, particularly type A, which could be due to a higher frequency of blood transfusions (32).

Conclusion

The findings showed a significant prevalence of HBV in Birnin Kebbi, with males and those aged 21-30 to 31-40 being the most affected. Furthermore, it is more common among those with ABO blood groups O+, A+, and B+. The study found no significant connection ($P > 0.05$) between age groups, genders, blood groups, and HBV prevalence. Based on these findings, there is an urgent need for public awareness of the dangers presented by HBV and its mechanisms of

transmission, particularly among men and carriers of ABO blood groups O+, A+, and B+ in the metropolis. Vaccination and regular screening of people for early detection of diseases are strongly recommended. Furthermore, blood donors should be screened for hepatitis. Similar research to the current study should be undertaken on a regular basis, with greater sample sizes and coverage of more hospitals.

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